

Bama's *Karukku* as an Intersectional Critique of Indian Knowledge Systems

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ABSTRACT

For centuries, the gender discrimination has been prevalent in Indian society. When it is about the Dalit community, the woman is marginalized thrice, in terms of caste, class and gender. Writing an autobiography is a special act for these women writers who use the genre to achieve a sense of identity and resistance against different forms of oppression. As a Dalit Christian Bama depicts her existential predicament: her struggle against patriarchy, class, caste and religion in her autobiographical text, *Karukku*, which is considered as the first autobiography written by a Dalit Christian woman. In her writings, Bama brings all the marginalized identities- Tamil, Dalit, Christian and Woman- under single canopy with synonymous understanding which challenges the mainstream aesthetic and reveals the real sufferings of a self as well as community. The present paper brings forth the subversive quality of Dalit women's writings that not only challenge a caste-stratified social system but also defies the patriarchal domination that exists both within and outside Dalit community. Bama's autobiographical text is thus studied as a counter-narrative to the mainstream literature to understand the multiple ways in which the issues of caste, gender and class intersect with each other, and how intersectionality and feminist stand point offer an effective analytical tool to study the text. Such an intersectional analysis in the context of gender, caste and class, has been done in the present paper. This paper also proposes to explore how Bama's writing compels readers to acknowledge the gaps in the existing body of "Indian Knowledge". Her writing also urges to consider how a more inclusive understanding of Indian society requires incorporating the perspectives and experiences of marginalized communities. *Karukku* stands as a pivotal work in Dalit literature and feminist discourse, voicing the unique experiences and struggles of Dalit women. Bama's journey in the autobiographical work is a quest for self-discovery and reclaiming agency, enabling her to challenge dominant narratives and assert her rights.

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KEYWORDS:

Identity, Intersectionality, Dalit feminism, marginalization, resistance, empowerment, agency, education, social change.

In a literary landscape long dominated by upper-caste and male voices, the writings of Dalit women have emerged as a critical and trans-formative force by providing an essential "insider perspective". Their writings directly challenge the established Indian knowledge systems by foregrounding the intersectional oppression of caste, class, and gender, offering a powerful counter-narrative to centuries of exclusion. This marginalized knowledge includes experiential understanding of societal issues, forms of literature, and practical knowledge of their environments and livelihoods, often unrecorded in

traditional texts, that offer alternative insights into social justice, cultural practices and the lived realities of a significant portion of the Indian population. For India's education policy to be egalitarian, it must substantively include Dalit pedagogical practices and voices, moving beyond mere formal inclusion to address historical marginalization. In the book, *Writing a Woman's Life*, critic Carolyn Heilburn observed, "Only in the last third of the twentieth century have women broken through to a realization of the narratives that have been controlling their lives" (60). This observation clearly reflects the truth

that in recent past women had begun to assert their power and control through their writings rather than being silenced by patriarchal literary tradition in centuries before. The oppression of the Dalit women is caused by the multiple factors of the social set up. It does not exhibit the events occurred in Bama's life in a chronological order. These are grouped and shown in different perspectives which enable Bama to discover herself as a woman, a Dalit and a Christian and find her rightful place in society. Bama as the chief exponent of the Tamil Dalit feminist writing, draws upon an intersectional framework in her writings to challenge the multiple oppressions of caste, gender, class and reflect the marginalized women's feminist consciousness. The present paper proposes to explore how Bama's magnum opus *Karukku* compels readers to acknowledge the gaps in the existing body of "Indian Knowledge" and to consider how a more inclusive understanding of Indian society requires incorporating the perspectives and experiences of marginalized communities.

The theory of intersectionality was coined and defined by the leading scholar Kimberle Crenshaw as "the various way[s] in which race and gender interact to shape the multiple dimensions of black women's experiences" (1989). The theory comes as a reaction to mainstream feminist theory's exclusion of those who are marginalized. Intersectional feminist theory or intersectional feminism aims to "[conceptualize] the relation between systems of oppression which construct our multiple identities and our social locations in hierarchies of power and privilege." (Carastathis, 2014) Hence an intersectional study allows to understand how gender notions originate in context of race, class, caste, nationality and other types of cultural identities. The theory empowers the gendered subaltern to challenge the mainstream and deconstruct established belief about their identity. The caste system is identified as a stratification system in Indian society where Dalits are continually considered as the lower strata of the society, whereas Dalit women are thought to be the 'other' of Dalit males to face various overlapping oppressions. Her protest against caste discrimination, intertwined with the hurt, humiliation, pain and angst of existence, provides a compelling challenge to the established idea of Dalit, particularly Dalit woman. Karan Singh rightly observes in locating woman in Dalit literature that "In the identification of a dalit woman, both the words 'dalit' and 'woman' define as well as limit her. The epithet 'dalit' makes her a part of subaltern segment of Hindu society; the nomenclature 'woman' further degrades her in a society of hierarchical power relationships" (220).

The writings of Dalit women offer a unique and vital 'Dalit feminist standpoint' that enriches and complicates the Indian Knowledge system. Sharmila Rege in her article, 'Dalit Women Talk Differently' proposes a standpoint perspective and emphasizes that "this requires a sharp focus on the processes by which gender, race, class, caste, sexuality—all construct each-other". Anandita Pan followed Rege and puts up her argument in favor of Dalit Feminism "as a transformative interpretative framework which," she explains, "I term dalit feminist intersectional standpoint. As an intersectional standpoint, Dalit Feminism looks at how the systems of caste and gender function intersectionally. The focus on the process and functionality of systemic oppression expands our understanding of how these systems operate in other instances as well as an intersectional standpoint." (Pan, 7) Hence, intersectionality is not about privileging gender over caste, race and ethnicity rather intersectional reading offers a different analysis of the issue underlining how the dominant interpretation overlooks the gender issues and conveniently sums up the problems as caste atrocity. So, intersectionality and feminist stand point offer an effective analytical tool to study Bama's personal narrative. By articulating their experiences, the Dalit women not only document the thrice marginalization but also create a new literary aesthetic, rooted in an honest and unapologetic portrayal of their reality along with its consequential voices of protests.

In her autobiographical text *Karukku* (1992), Bama chronicles the joys and sorrows experienced by Dalit Christian women in Tamil Nadu. The autobiography is a narrative of three-fold subjugation of Dalit Christian woman. Bama is the spokesperson of all the Dalit women, especially of the converted Christians who, in spite of the conversion, suffered at three levels- as women, as Dalits and as poor. Dalit women are supposed to remain under the clutches of patriarchal Indian set up. In *Karukku*, she has depicted all such incidents where she has experienced exploitation and suppression of Dalit women. Bama is one of the prominent Dalit writers who highlighted the plight of Dalits of paraiya community in general and the women in particular. *Karukku* focuses on the various aspects of the community such as caste, gender, poverty and religion that caused a great pain in Bama's personal life. Thus, Bama's *Karukku* discusses how Dalits face a variety of discrimination and victimization—prohibited from eating with other caste-members, separate glasses for them in village tea stalls, discriminatory seating arrangements in functions and festivals of village, prohibited from entering village temples, prohibited from wearing sandals or holding umbrellas in front of dominant

caste members, Devadasi system (the ritualized temple prostitution of Dalit women), prohibited from using common village paths, separate burial grounds, no access to common amenities and resources of villages and segregation of Dalit children in schools. Her autobiographical work problematizes the issues of caste, class and gender in an Indian context. It glorifies the woman's discovery of selfhood and her assertion through her constant struggle with poverty, caste barriers and patriarchy. The title is very symbolic. Bama considers the life of a Dalit female as 'Karukku' as a Dalit woman has to face the two-edged oppression, i.e. the oppression by patriarchy on the one side and by class hegemony on the other. *Karukku* functions as a counter-narrative by using a testimonial style to expose the systematic oppression of Dalit women, challenging the celebratory, upper-caste narratives of post- Independence India. It reclaims the agency of the oppressed by shifting the narrative perspective from a marginalized "other" to a collective, first-person "we" to prioritize the collective experience. This autobiographical work, having a disjointed, thematic structure reflecting the intricacy of identity and memory, also challenges the conventional, ordered structure of upper caste narratives. As Sagita Patil Sharnappa observes, "Bama's *Karukku* represents the most traumatic and suffocating lives of Dalits. It is not an armchair reading, but transits mind and heart and makes the reader to introspect and brood over it. It is also a spiritual journey and quest for identity and integrity" (Sharnappa, 68).

Bama who inherits her subaltern marginalized identity as a Dalit Christian, stood as a vibrant mouthpiece of the Dalits, reflecting the sentiments of the oppressed classes. Her traumatic and claustrophobic life becomes a part of Dalit sufferings and marginalization. Her inherited social identity is emblematic and symbolic representation of oppressed Dalit society in India that lacks voice to protest against the mainstream Indian society. Bama starts her narration by describing her village, her childhood, her education, her Christian upbringing, her joining the Catholic order as a Nun and her subsequent return to her community. In the text, *Karukku*, the protagonist belongs to the Paraya caste, and surrounded by higher caste groups like Nadar, Naicker, Chettiyaar, Aasaari, Thevar etc. Bama narrates the traditional and cultural ill treatment done to them by the higher caste groups. The Paraya caste women are always bound to display their regard and servitude towards upper caste people and also within their household. About Parayar community Bama writes as "...the poorest of poor, struggling for daily survival, doesn't need spelling out." (79) The feeling

of caste-consciousness in Bama is very strong as she started reacting, to stand against the traditional hierarchy of caste prevalent in society. By weaving together different stages and memories at her village, at school and church to coming to maturity as a Dalit, Bama emphasizes the continuous inescapable nature of caste-based prejudice throughout her life. She condemns the hypocrisy of Hindu society, which advocates caste divisions and keeps a segment of people as lower than animals. According to the notions of the upper caste people, as Bama writes in *Karukku*, "... low-caste people are all degraded in every way. They think we have no moral discipline nor cleanliness nor culture. They think that this can never be changed... In this society, if you are born into a low caste, you are forced to live a life of humiliation and degradation until your death." (26)

Bama's journey in the autobiographical work is a quest for self-discovery and reclaiming agency, enabling her to challenge dominant narratives and assert her rights. The use of colloquial language, along with the integration of local dialect, proverbs, folk songs and anecdotes, challenges the supremacy of canon language and elevates Dalit women's voices and vernacular expression. As Dr. G. Krishnakumari writes, "Bama's *Karukku* has a tale that exhibits both a simplistic and profound structure, as it explores the experiences of a Dalit lady. The piece of art effectively challenges the established norms and discourse of the male Dalit narrative by employing unconventional plot structures, a dynamic timeline, fragmented storytelling, unidentified characters, and the incorporation of vernacular language. Bama deliberately deviates from the conventional format typically seen in autobiographies in order to effectively convey her unique perspective as a marginalized individual within the context of gender." (Krishnakumari, 40)

This deliberate stylistic choice is a powerful tool for self-representation and assertion for Bama. Her work is rooted in and offers voice to the ancient, suppressed forms of knowledge passed down through generations within her own Paraiyar Dalit community. This includes oral traditions, vernacular dialects, and the embodied knowledge of resistance and survival which eventually reject the "sanskritized" or standard Tamil imposed by the dominant culture considering Dalit dialects as unrefined.

In Bama's autobiographical text, the sufferings of women in the Dalit community in multiple ways are portrayed right from a young girl to an old woman. Dalit women suffer more than Dalit men in this caste-based system. Be it in a clash in terms of religion, caste, for land or whatever, it is Dalit women who are

the oppressed one, not just by the upper caste Hindu men, but by Hindu women too. *Karukku* questions several patriarchal rules existing in the society which oppress and suppress the women. Bama explores the hardships and everyday reality of Dalit women. She projects herself questioning various post-colonial and traditional oppressions. Women are portrayed as the wage workers who play a significant role in supporting the family with their everyday income. But they are not paid the amount as men were paid. As Bama writes,

“When I saw our people working so hard night and day, I often used to wonder from where they got their strength. And I used to think, that at the rate they worked, men and women both, every single day, they should really be able to advance themselves. But of course, they never received a payment that was appropriate to their labour. And another thing. Even if they did the same work, men received one wage, women another. They always paid men more. I could never understand why.” (*Karukku*, 54-55)

The autobiographical text also emphasizes the transformative power of education for Dalit individuals, especially women to find their voice, assert their rights and achieve self-identity by challenging the caste-based discrimination and gender stereotypes prevalent in society. In Bama's case, the major encouragement came from her elder brother, Raj Gowthaman. She could study only up to VIII in their village. In that village, High School is also there but that was meant for the upper caste children only. Dalits could not be admitted there. Dalits had to go to high school in another village, which is about two-three kilometers away. Her father encouraged her a lot and said these words, ‘whether you marry or not, you must have an education and a profession so that you can stand on your own two feet’. The narrative presents many forms of violence and oppression that Dalit women have to torment. As Lakshmi Holmstorm opines in *Karukku*, “Bama captures a moment that contains a paradox: she seeks an identity, but seeks a change which means an end to that identity” (x). The meaning of the novel and its effect lies in this ‘inherent contradiction’, the contrasting and contradicting usage of caste-talk as a tool to destroy casteism. Bama's *Karukku* discusses how Dalits face a variety of discrimination and victimization—prohibited from eating with other caste-members, separate glasses for them in village tea stalls, discriminatory seating arrangements in functions and festivals of village, prohibited from entering village temples, prohibited from wearing sandals or holding umbrellas in front of dominant caste members, Devadasi system (the ritualized

temple prostitution of Dalit women), prohibited from using common village path, separate burial grounds, no access to common amenities and resources of villages and segregation of Dalit children in schools. According to Bama, as her brother opines, “‘Because we are born into the Paraya jati, we are never given any honour or dignity or respect. We are stripped off all that. But if we study and make progress, we can throw away these indignities. So, study with care, learn all you can. If you are always ahead in your lessons, people will come to you of their own accord and attach themselves to you. Work hard and learn.’ The words that Annan spoke to me that day made a very deep impression on me. And I studied hard, with all my breath and being, in a frenzy almost.” (17-18)

In her autobiography, Bama narrates how during her school and college days the lower caste students were regularly being harassed by the upper caste teachers without any reason. Bama never expected that in the church-run schools and colleges, caste discrimination would exist because the church preached equality for all. Many a times she herself was a victim of such discrimination. But Bama never lost her heart. She had by then realized that education was the only way for Dalits to improve their degraded conditions. Her immediate examples were, her father who was serving in the Indian army and her elder brother Annan who had completed his post-graduation. With perseverance and hard work Bama successfully completed her college education and got an offer to teach in the convent where she was studying earlier. After many years of hard work, she was now employed with a regular income. So, it was definitely happy moment for Bama and her family members. However, Bama could not continue her job for long. After joining the convent, she understood that it was a place only for the people who belonged to the privileged sections. The poor and Dalits were humiliated there by the nuns who mostly came from the upper caste families. Finally, Bama resigned from the job after a realization that “why should I not become a nun too and truly help these people who are humiliated so much and kept under such strict control?” Truly she finds her ‘self’ in expressing her opinions, raising her voice, questioning the society for their discrimination in the name of caste, class and gender. She took writing as her weapon and stood as a spokesperson of her community. She protests against the age-old oppression and becomes successful in asserting identity, voice to the voiceless.

Through her writings, Bama is able to reflect the voices of the Paraiyar in an open, bold discourse bringing a sense of dignity and honor to her community. She interrogates dominant literary

practices and articulates the experience of the oppressed in the language of the oppressed. As Raj Kumar has rightly pointed out, “what is significant about Bama’s autobiography is that apart from being a literary masterpiece it is a rare social document prepared by a Dalit woman activist. The new insights that come from her life’s experiences will certainly give new direction to Dalit movements which otherwise are lacking in leadership from women.... She does bring across issues related to Dalit women but only in the context of her community and never as a single-issue concerning women’s identity. *Karukku*, in fact, celebrates the rich cultural heritage of the paraya community and it is women who through their rituals, festivals and day-to-day household duties prove to be custodians of that rich culture. Bama also displays Dalit women’s indomitable courage to withstand many social pressures including police atrocities. By highlighting such issues Bama emphasizes the important role played by Dalit women in their communities.” (Raj Kumar, 237)

Bama’s narrative showcases the importance of perseverance and the pursuit of knowledge to overcome the inherent difficulties and discrimination in accessing quality education. This act highlights Bama’s personal ways of defiance against oppressive structures as well as the strength of community solidarity and collective action among Dalit women highlighting their resilience in the face of shared struggles. Bama’s experiences within the educational system act as a critique of social injustices and a powerful call for greater access to education and equality for Dalit women. In essence, *Karukku* re-defines Dalit identity as a symbol of shared experiences, resilience and a fight for recognition to build a more just and equitable world. Thus, in her autobiographical novel, *Karukku*, Bama significantly redefines what constitutes “Indian knowledge” by challenging dominant narratives, elevating Dalit voices and perspectives, focusing on the intersection of caste, gender and religion, and reclaiming self-esteem and identity.

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